

Horizon Europe

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Briefing Paper 1

Critical Interpretative Synthesis Process Protocol: Locating Publications for Reviewing

Action **The affective economies of emerging private renting markets: understanding tenants and landlords in postcommunist Romania (AFFECTIVE-PRS)**

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1. Project Summary

The 2008 Global Financial Crisis and the Covid-19 pandemic have exposed rental housing as a mechanism that generates important inequalities of wealth, health and wellbeing in much of the world, while failing to give many tenants a 'home'. Academic interest in the Anglo-Saxon and the old EU member states has recently contributed disturbing insights (e.g. poor housing quality, insecurity, eviction, economic stress), raising legitimate concerns about tenants' wellbeing in the more hidden, hence riskier private renting sectors (PRS) where informal transactions increase risks and hide vulnerability away from state regulatory gaze.

Sharing these important concerns, AFFECTIVE-PRS project engages with the affective economies of emerging, 'hidden' PRS, taking as a case-study the post-communist space, specifically Romania. It aims to: **Understand** a hidden social world, by asking why tenants and landlords engage in the sector, whether their practices permit making a private tenancy home, and how they construct ideas of power, risk and trust; **Advance** theory by conceiving home as an assemblage of materials, money, relations and affects; **Inform** the national and international debate on PRS regulation.

Methodologically, this project will develop a synthesis of the international literature (**to which this Briefing Paper relates**); will approach tenants and landlords through an online qualitative questionnaire, which allows them to freely and fully describe their experiences; photo-elicitation interviews to obtain deeper insights; and a co-production workshop with policy, practice and academia in order to imagine a sustainable and fair PRS in Romania and inform the national debate on its regulation.

As the PRS generates important inequalities of wealth and wellbeing, it is important to maximize the project impact. Academic impact will be attained through publications and dissemination through conferences, seminars and workshops. Findings will be communicated to the general public through briefing papers, blogs, media articles and a "Guide for Good Practice" as well as through interactive digital platforms. By helping **construct a shared understanding of good practice** in the PRS, the project could theoretically improve the lives of many private tenants, whether it be the officially registered 252,000 or the over one million estimated.

2. The Aim of the Method

The Critical Interpretative Synthesis (CIS) is a novel approach to reviewing (Depraetere et al. 2020), ‘*a methodology that enables synthesis of large amounts of diverse qualitative data and facilitates critical engagement with the assumptions that shape and inform a body of research*’ (Farias and Laliberte Rudman 2016). This CIS addresses the international component of Objective One – that is understanding tenants’ and landlords’ motivations and practices beyond the over-studied Anglo-Saxon and Western Europe states – through a systematic review of the existing literature. The specific research questions to be addressed under Objective One are:

RQ1: Why do tenants and landlords engage in the PRS?

RQ2: What are their affective and material practices of constructing a sense of home in a privately rented property?

RQ3: How do they construct ideas of power, risk and trust when navigating market transactions, state regulations and cultural understandings?

This CIS builds on a more feasible approach to reviewing as well as on prior experience (Soaita et al. 2021; Soaita et al. 2019b) in that it draws and expands my colleagues’ and my own synthesis on tenants’ experiences in Anglo-Saxon countries (Soaita et al. 2020) to global geographies while also including landlords’ experiences. CIS does not require ethical approval.

3. Aim of this Briefing Paper

This Briefing Paper 1 reports the step-by-step process of, and the decisions taken in identifying the literature to be reviewed. It contributes to making AFFECTIVE-PRS research data FAIR that is more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable by other academic users. While the paper demonstrates the rigor of the methodological approach taken, it also opens up the space for other scholars to scrutinise, replicate or adjust this approach to their own work. This Briefing Paper 1 documents:

- ✚ Preliminary decisions on the breadth of the review (section 4)
- ✚ Operationalisation of the searching strings (section 5)
- ✚ A pilot of keywords and searching strings to understand results (section 6)
- ✚ The parameters of the final systematic and hand-made searches (section 7)
- ✚ A step-by-step summary of the process of identifying the relevant publications (section 8)

Findings, including coding, text extraction and data analysis/interpretation will be presented in a follow up Briefing Paper.

4. Preliminary Decisions

To match the AFFECTIVE-PRS resources while reaching searches of enough bibliographical breadth and retrieving publications of academic quality, the following restrictive decisions were taken from the start to construct the systematic searches. These restrictive decisions will inevitably lead to some relevant references being missed, however, as common practice, systematic searches will be complemented by hand-made searches in a limited number of key journals as well as by peer recommendations.

4.1 Choice of databases

To review *systematically* but *not exhaustively* the published literature on tenants' and landlords' experiences of renting, the large and complementary databases of SCOPUS and Web of Science were chosen (Soaita et al. 2019b).

4.2 Searching fields

Based on prior experience (Soaita et al. 2019a; Soaita et al. 2021; Soaita et al. 2019b), searches will be performed in the fields of title, abstract and keywords in SCOPUS and topic in Web of Science in order to get the most relevant results.

4.3 Type of research

Given the qualitative nature of the research questions, a decision was made to look exclusively for qualitative research, expanding thus Soaita's et al (2020) approach beyond the Anglo-Saxon countries.

4.4 Type of references

Following others (Lee et al. 2015; Soaita et al. 2021; Wang et al. 2016), as a way to proxy research quality, a decision was made to include only journal articles, books and book chapters.

5. The Searching Strings

Drawing on Cooke et al (2012), the three searching strings aimed to capture the groups of interest (tenants and landlords), the field of housing (rather than other rental markets, e.g. land, commercial property) and the methodology (i.e. qualitative research). The respective searching strings 1, 2 and 3 in Table 1 were inspired by Soaita et al (2020) and Liu et al (2021), expanded to landlords as well as refined (by adding some additional keywords related to the field of housing).

The operationalisation of each searching strings aimed to be inclusive to a few key meta-categories (e.g. housing, qualitative) as well as targeting certain key under-categories (e.g. flatmate, rooming house) in such a way that, taken together, they would return the most relevant publications. However, any searching string must be piloted to understand the structure of the publications so retrieved. Given its analytical tools, SCOPUS is particularly useful for preliminary piloting.

Table 1 The searching strings

Strings	Fields	Operationalisation
String 1	Tenants OR landlords	(private AND (tenant* OR renter*)) OR lodger* OR squatter* OR flatmate* OR (HMO* AND resident*) OR (HMO* AND tenant*) OR (private AND landlord*) OR (tenant* AND landlord*) OR (landlord*-tenant* OR tenant*-landlord*)
String 2	Housing	(housing OR home OR house OR flat OR apartment OR flat-share OR (hous* AND "in multiple occupation") OR (rooming AND hous*) OR (boarding AND hous*) OR (Rooming AND hous*))
String 3	Method	(qualitative OR interview OR ethnograph* OR "case study" OR "case studies")

6. Piloting the Searching Strings: A SCOPUS Exercise

6.1 Piloting the keywords

Each keyword in Table 1 was piloted separately in SCOPUS (9 Jan 2023). The process revealed the association between certain keywords and disciplines (e.g. flat* and flat-mate* returned many hits in the physical sciences and boarding-hous* in biology and veterinary), but these associations weakened when targeted on the remaining two strings. Targeting the first-round returns on the housing string resulted in a reduction of 62% on average; further targeting the returns on the method string resulted in a further reduction of 79% on average.

Table 2 Checking the operationalisation of keywords (SCOPUS)

	Returns		Targeted on the housing string		Further targeted on the method string	
	All countries	AUS, GBR, NZL, USA	All countries	AUS, GBR, NZL, USA	All countries	AUS, GBR, NZL, USA
	No.	% of all	No.	% of all	No.	% of all
private AND renter*	292	72%	254	76%	60	80%
private AND landlord*	617	51%	429	56%	99	60%
tenant* AND landlord*	1,578	55%	799	60%	179	65%

Given AFFECTIVE-PRS research interest in non-Anglo-Saxon geographies, the size of the literature related to Australia, New Zealand, the UK and the USA was monitored. Not unlike other studies (Liu et al. 2021; Soaita et al. 2021), the piloting exercise gave a first impression of the dominance of the Anglo-Saxon literature (see Table 2 below for three examples and Table 3 and 4 in the Annex for more).

6.2 Setting additional exclusion criteria

The SCOPUS literature was then retrieved (on 10 Jan 2023) with the three strings combined (“String 1 AND String 2 AND String 3”). A total of 529 references of articles, book and book chapters were returned. Examining the features of the returned references, further decisions of exclusions were made based on:

- ✚ Discipline (35 references were excluded)¹
- ✚ Language (13 were excluded for being written in a language other than English)
- ✚ Publishing timeline (12 references published between 1973 and 1989 were excluded). This decision was also supported by the fact that a systematic review of the pre-1992 published literature on rental housing already existed (Rakodi 1995).

Overall, it was decided that taken together, the three strings combined with the excluding criteria above returned a literature that is focused enough on the topic and large enough to obtain geographical, substantive and theoretical diversity.

¹ Earth and Planetary Sciences; Agricultural and Biological Sciences; Mathematics; Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology; Physics and Astronomy; Veterinary.

6.3 Mapping geographical coverage

The remaining sample (n=469) was downloaded in an EndNote database, coded for countries of the case studies and mapped in order to observe geographical coverage. As already indicated and not unlike other studies (Liu et al. 2021), results showed the dominance of Anglo-Saxon literature (and some western European countries) across the geographies of the case-studies (Figure 1, next page) as well as in terms of institutional affiliation, authorship and funding (Figure 2 in the Annex).

Figure 1 also shows the lack of representation of many countries across the globe, particularly Eurasia and Africa. While Liu et al (2021) observed that China was well represented in the economic housing literature, i.e. being second after the USA, this was not the case under this study's methodological and thematic criteria.

6.4 Capturing the 'Majority World'

To capture emergent, 'hidden' private renting markets, the Anglo-Saxon countries (with lightly regulated PRS), the old members and associates of the EU/EEA (with stronger regulated markets) and a few developed other countries (Canada, Japan) are excluded on theoretical grounds. This is not to say that informal renting arrangements are non-existent in these countries but they are numerically marginal (Morris et al. 2021):

✚ Excluded countries (in three-letter acronym): AUS, AUT, BEL, CAN, CHE, DEU, DNK, ELA, ESP, FIN, FRA, GBR, GRC, IRL, ITA, ISL, JPN, LIE, LUX, MLT, NLD, NOR, NZL, PRT, SWE, USA.

Given the very uneven countries' representation of what is sometimes referred to as the 'Majority World' (Simone and Fauzan 2013), a decision was made to include all countries notwithstanding their significantly different context of renting. For a similar approach see Kholodilin (2020).

7. Retrieving and Identifying the Literature to be Reviewed

Once the exclusion/inclusion criteria have been calibrated to the study's aim, the literature was retrieved through systematic searches in SCOPUS (see section 7.1) and Web of Science (see section 7.2). After merging and checking these returns for relevance (section 7.3), the sample was enhanced with additional hand-made searches in key journals (see section 7.4).

Figure 1 The global spread of the (SCOPUS) retrieved literature

By the author

Base map by Egs, CC BY-SA 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=5688632>

7.1 Retrieving from SCOPUS

🚩 **Boolean string:** (TITLE-ABS-KEY ((private AND (tenant* OR renter*)) OR lodger* OR squatter* OR flatmate* OR (hmo* AND resident*) OR (hmo* AND tenant*) OR (private AND landlord*) OR (tenant* AND landlord*) OR (landlord*-tenant* OR tenant*-landlord*)) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ((housing OR home OR house OR flat OR apartment OR flat-share OR (hous* AND "in multiple occupation") OR (rooming AND hous*) OR (boarding AND hous*))) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ((qualitative OR interview OR ethnograph* OR "case study" OR "case studies"))) AND (EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "United Kingdom") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "United States") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Australia") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Canada") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Sweden") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Germany") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Netherlands") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Italy") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Japan") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "New Zealand") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Denmark") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Ireland") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Norway") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Spain") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Austria") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Belgium") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "France") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Switzerland") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Portugal") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Cyprus") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Finland")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ch") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "re") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "bk")) AND (EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1989) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1988) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1987) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1986) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1985) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1984) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1982) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1976)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "MEDI") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "EART") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "AGRI") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "BIOC"))

🚩 **Notes:** Not all excluded countries or years were represented (hence only those represented could be excluded in the Boolean string above)

🚩 **Returns:** 90 references, imported into EndNote

7.2 Retrieving from Web of Science

🚩 **Boolean string:** (private AND (tenant* OR renter*)) OR lodger* OR squatter* OR flatmate* OR (HMO* AND resident*) OR (HMO* AND tenant*) OR (private AND landlord*) OR (tenant* AND landlord*) OR (landlord*-tenant* OR tenant*-landlord*) (Topic) AND (housing OR home OR house OR flat OR apartment OR flat-share OR (hous* AND "in multiple occupation") OR (rooming AND hous*) OR (boarding AND hous*)) (Topic) AND (qualitative OR interview OR

ethnograph* OR “case study” OR “case studies”) (Topic) and Infectious Diseases or Forestry or Water Resources or Genetics Heredity or Mathematical Computational Biology or Archaeology or Biochemistry Molecular Biology or Biotechnology Applied Microbiology or Chemistry or Critical Care Medicine or Emergency Medicine or Imaging Science Photographic Technology or Instruments Instrumentation or Mechanics or Medical Ethics or Neurosciences Neurology or Oceanography or Parasitology or Physics or Polymer Science or Food Science Technology or Meteorology Atmospheric Sciences or Pharmacology Pharmacy or Plant Sciences or Zoology or Agriculture or Geriatrics Gerontology or Veterinary Sciences or Surgery or Mathematics or Nutrition Dietetics or Geology or Immunology or Obstetrics Gynecology or Gastroenterology Hepatology (Exclude – Research Areas) and English (Languages) and ENGLAND or USA or UNITED KINGDOM or AUSTRALIA or CANADA or SCOTLAND or SWEDEN or NETHERLANDS or GERMANY or ITALY or NEW ZEALAND or NORWAY or DENMARK or FRANCE or NORTH IRELAND or SPAIN or BELGIUM or IRELAND or FINLAND or GREECE or UK or AUSTRIA or or JAPAN or PORTUGAL or SWITZERLAND or WALES (Exclude – Countries/Regions)

✚ **Notes:** Not all excluded countries or years were represented (hence only those represented could be excluded in the Boolean string above)

✚ **Returns:** 64 references, imported into EndNote

7.3 Checking for relevance

Notwithstanding the precision of the searching strings and the automatic EndNote removal of duplicate references (as some are indexed in multiple databases), the retrieved literature must be manually checked for criteria fit. Of the 154 retrieved references, 31 were retained for reviewing.

Of the excluded references, 41 were duplicates; a few were excluded for language misfit, country misfit or for being inaccessible. Many more were excluded for thematic misfit (n=62), their focus being on public/social renting, general housing/renting policies, homeownership while others used quantitative methods or were tenure-blind in their discussion. Box 1 in the Annex lists the excluded references by grounds of exclusion; some of these were however put aside for setting the policy context.

7.4 Performing hand-searches

Once the 31 relevant publications discovered through systematic searches were identified, good practice recommends enhancing the sample through hand-made searches in key journals, peer recommendations, and inclusion of some of the references of the identified publications (Arksey and

O'Malley 2005; Barnett-Page and Thomas 2009; Carroll et al. 2011; Cooke et al. 2012; Erasmus et al. 2014; Evans and Benefield 2001).

As the 31 references were spread across very different journals (none featuring more than twice), the selection of journals for further hand-made searches was rather subjective: the journals of *Housing Studies* and the *International Journal of Housing Policy* were selected for their international focus on housing; *Geoforum* and *Urban Studies* for their international albeit broader substantive focus; and *Habitat International* for its particular focus on developing countries; *Google Scholar* was also used.

In total, 38 references were added to the sample. Based on extensive previous experience (Soaita 2018a; Soaita 2018b; Soaita et al. 2019a; Soaita et al. 2021; Soaita et al. 2020; Soaita et al. 2019b; Soaita et al. 2022), it was considered that a sample of 69 publications can be attended to within the resource constraints of the study while being large enough to deliver theoretical and geographical nuance. The decision to close the sample was also supported by the fact that peer-recommended references were already captured, however, the author maintains the right to add and review new references if particularly relevant (e.g. by checking the reference list of the retrieved publications).

8. Summary of the Process

Table 3 summarises the process, showing the steps, the action, the number of references at the end of each action, and explanatory notes.

Table 3 Summary of the process

Steps	Action	No.	Explanatory notes
S1	Preliminary steps		Setting the parameters of the systematic searches (e.g. choice of databases, searching fields, type of reference, discipline, publishing timeline, geography). Piloting of the searching strings, independently and together, is essential for good calibration.
S2	Retrieved	154	Systematic searches were performed in SCOPUS and Web of Science on 10 Jan 2023 with the Boolean strings shown in section 5. In total, 154 references were exported in an EndNote database.
S3	Unique references	120	Following EndNote automatic removal of duplicates, a total of 120 unique references remained (101 journal articles; 11 books; 8 book chapters).
S4	Manual check for criteria fit (in titles,	31	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 89 references were excluded for language misfit (n=1), could not be accessed (n=6), were previously unrecognised duplicates (n=7), country misfit (n=13) and thematic misfit (n=62). See Box 1.

	abstracts and full text)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 31 references were retained: 29 articles; 1 book chapter, 2 books (26% relevant hits of the total retrieved).
S5	Boosting the sample with manual searches	69	<p>Searches/inquiries were performed in the order below (17-20 Jan 2023):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 9 additional references were identified in Housing Studies, out of the first most-relevant 300 publications; keyword: “renting”, which also returned “rented, rental or rent” (3.0% relevant hits of the total) • 3 additional references were identified in the International Journal of Housing Policy, out of the first most-relevant 300 publications; keyword: “renting”, which also returned “rented, rental or rent” (1.0% relevant hits of the total). • 3 additional references were identified in Geoforum, out of the first most-relevant 400 publications; separate searches with the keywords: “renting” and “housing”; (0.8% relevant hits of the total). • 13 additional references were identified in Habitat International, out of the first most-relevant 300 publications; keyword: “renting” (4.3% relevant hits of the total). • 7 additional references were identified in Urban Studies, out of the first most-relevant 300 publications (searches for “renting”; 2.3% relevant hits of the total) • 3 additional references were identified in Google Scholar, out of the first 300 publications (searches for “renting”; 1.0% relevant hits of the total) • 0 additional publications identified through peer/expert recommendations. • A number of more publications may be added in the process of reading the 69 identified ones (checking their list of references).

The list of publications to be reviewed is shown in Box 2 in the Annex.

Figure 2 displays the geographical distribution of all publications. We note that:

- many countries remained uncaptured in the sample;
- 16 countries are represented by just one publication;
- Eight countries are represented with between 2 and 5 papers;
- Only four countries are represented with more than 5 papers.

The above observations already highlight the need for further research on the renting arrangements and experiences in the Majority World.

Figure 2 Country representation across the identified literature

Source: By the author

Base map by Egs, CC BY-SA 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=5688632>

Figure 3 Publishing timeline

The publishing timeline of the 69 references retained for reviewing is shown in Figure 3. We note that most references were published after 2000 (n=57 making 83% of the total).

In addition to the 69 publications retained for reviewing, a number of 59 papers were retained to provide general context on housing policies in the Global South, including two systematic reviews of the rental tenure (Gilbert 2016; Rakodi 1995).²

9. Conclusion

This Briefing Paper 1 has aimed to contribute to making AFFECTIVE-PRS research data FAIR that is more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable by other academic users. It has demonstrated the rigour of the methodological approach taken to identifying the relevant publications to be reviewed despite it being tailored to the limited resources of this study. The paper has also aimed at opening the space for other scholars to scrutinise, replicate, or adjust this approach to their own work. The paper has described the parameters that set the breadth of the review; the operationalisation and piloting of the Boolean strings for systematic searches; and a step-by-step summary of the process of identifying the 69 relevant publications to be reviewed.

Findings, including coding, text extraction and data analysis/interpretation will be presented in a follow up Briefing Paper.

² 2 Africa; 1 Argentina; 1 Asia; 1 Bangladesh; 8 China; 1 Eastern Europe; 5 Ghana; 3 Global South; 2 Hong Kong; 1 Hungary; 1 Indonesia; 6 India; 2 Kenya; 1 Latin America; 1 Mexico; 2 Malaysia; 3 Nigeria; 1 Pakistan; 1 South Africa; 2 South Korea; 7 Turkey; 1 Taiwan; 2 Tanzania; and 4 Theory.

Annex

Table 4 Checking the operationalisation of other participant groups' keywords

	Returns		Targeted on the housing string		Further targeted on the method string	
	All countries	AUS, GBR, NZL, USA	All countries	AUS, GBR, NZL, USA	All countries	AUS, GBR, NZL, USA
	nr	% of all	nr	% of all	nr	% of all
Private AND tenant*	1,145	51%	680	58%	166	60%
Lodger*	196	37%	74	33%	7	43%
Flatmate*	34	74%	15	93%	3	100%
Flat-mate*	220	30%	220	30%	5	40%
HMO* AND resident*	283	62%	69	83%	18	89%
HMO* AND tenant*	8	62%	8	62%	2	100%
squatter*	2,205	33%	880	22%	172	28%
Tenant*-landlord* OR Landlord*-tenant*	317	59%	150	63%	27	67%

Table 5 Checking the operationalisation of additional housing keywords

	Returns		Targeted on the tenant/landlord string		Further targeted on the method string	
	All countries	AUS, GBR, NZL, USA	All countries	AUS, GBR, NZL, USA	All countries	AUS, GBR, NZL, USA
	nr	% from all	nr	% from all	nr	% from all
Hous*AND "in multiple Occupation"	51	61%	0	0%	0	0%
Rooming AND hous*	101	37%	8	75%	4	50%
Boarding AND hous*	659	38%	13	62%	8	75%
Aparment*	20,631	25%	178	40%	34	50%

Figure 4 The Anglo-Saxon dominance in top 15 (SCOPUS retrieved literature)

Box 1 Excluded references by category of misfit**Language misfit**

1. Pérez, M., and Palma, C. (2021). "From foreigners to urban citizens: autoconstruction and migration in the Santiago Metropolitan Area." *Estudios Atacamenos*, 67, 1-21.

Not accessible

2. Bocutoğlu, E., and Ertürk, Z. (2006). "Supply and demand analysis in the housing market: a case study in Turkey as a developing country", *Management, Quality and Economics in Building*. CRC Press, pp. 1566-1572.
3. Brezar, V. (2012). "The future of urban dwelling design." *International Journal for Housing Science and Its Applications*, 36(2), 89-98.
4. Kamruzzaman, M. (2012). *Housing for the urban poor through informal providers, Dhaka, Bangladesh*.
5. Kayila, J. O. (2019). "Improving urban settlements for the poor: case studies of Dandora and Chaani projects in Kenya", *Reaching the Urban Poor: Project Implementation in Developing Countries*. Taylor and Francis, pp. 145-162.
6. Lee-Smith, D. (2018). "Squatter landlords in Nairobi: a case study of Korogocho", *Housing Africa'S Urban Poor: Volume 2*. Taylor and Francis, pp. 175-188.

Unrecognised duplicates

1. Akhtar, A. S., and Rashid, A. (2021). "Dispossession and the militarised developer state: financialisation and class power on the agrarian-urban frontier of Islamabad, Pakistan." *Third World Quarterly*, 42(8), 1866-1884.
2. Govender, V., and Loggia, C. (2021). "Adaptive reuse strategies in Durban inner city using hybrid mapping tools" *Urban Book Series*. Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH, pp. 219-250.
3. Govindasamy, A. R. (2010). "Indians and rural displacement: exclusion from region building in Malaysia." *Asian Journal of Political Science*, 18(1), 90-104.
4. Jackson, A., and Archer, C. D. (2022). "Factors influencing Jamaican householders' housing choice." *International Journal of Housing Markets and Analysis*, 15(5), 1053-1071.
5. Kotyk, L. (2020). "Governing without governed and governors: an attempt to establish a non-hierarchical organizational repertoire1." *Partecipazione e Conflitto*, 13(3), 1308-1323.
6. McKay, T., Fakudze, N., and Gunter, A. (2022). "The middle remains missing: class exclusion from the urban rental market in suburban Johannesburg." *Acta Academica*, 54(1), 113-133.
7. Yung, B., and Lee, F. P. (2014). "'Equal right to housing' in Hong Kong housing policy: perspectives from disadvantaged groups." *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*, 29(4), 563-582.

Country misfit

1. Bennett, J., Howden-Chapman, P., Chisholm, E., Keall, M., and Baker, M. G. (2016). "Towards an agreed quality standard for rental housing: field testing of a New Zealand housing WOF tool." *Australian and New Zealand journal of public health*, 40(5), 405-411.
2. Cox, G., and Phibbs, P. (1994). "Evaluation of a tenancy advice service case study of Waverley, Sydney." *Urban Policy and Research*, 12(1), 40-46.
3. Dorn, V. (1997). "Changes in the social rented sector in Germany." *Housing Studies*, 12(4), 463-475.
4. Kadir, N. (2016). *The autonomous life?: Paradoxes of hierarchy and authority in the squatters movement in Amsterdam*: Manchester University Press.
5. Kotyk, L. (2020). "Governing without governed and governors: an attempt to establish a non-hierarchical organizational repertoire1." *Partecipazione e Conflitto*, 13(3), 1308-1323.
6. Sim, D. (1996). "The Scottish house factoring profession." *Urban History*, 23(3), 351-370.
7. Smith, M. P. (2017). *Marginal spaces: Comparative urban and community research, volume 5*: Taylor and Francis.

8. Stanbury, W. T., and Todd, J. D. (1990). "Landlords as economic prisoners of war." *Canadian Public Policy/Analyse de Politiques*, 16(4), 399-417.
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